

FRACTURE ANALYSIS OF NEEDLE PUNCHED NONWOVEN COMPOSITE WITH OPEN HOLES

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1 General Introduction

It is very usual and effective to use joints in connecting different parts of structure. Three types of joints are usually used, including adhesively bonded joints, pinned or bolted joints known as mechanically fastened joint and the combination one [1-3]. Mechanically fastened joints is very convenient and common in the assembly of structural components, because of its advantage on transferring high load as composite materials, good resistant to interlaminar stresses and suitable for any environmental conditions [4]. However, due to stress concentration around holes in joints, it is more likely to occur initial localized failure and significantly reducing the loading capacity of materials. In order to improve the property of joints and provide theory supports to design, both open and filled-hole tension tests have been widely investigated in the industry.

During the past 30 years, notched strength was investigated extensively as an important parameter in design process. It was extensively used in application and design. During tensile test process, the stress concentration happens near the hole and causes initial damage. Many factors can affects the notched strength, including thickness, notched size and geometry, ply orientation and so on [5-6]. The notched strength was also deeply affected by fiber configuration [7].

It is obvious that laminated composites have poor strength in direction perpendicular to plane. From the research of Wisom and Hallett [8], the damage mechanism of open-hole materials during tension was evaluated. It was found that delamination has a crucial role in the in-plane strength, failure mechanism and hole size effect in open-hole tension of quasi-isotropic laminates, and can lead to premature failure, especially for small holes and thick ply blocks. In order to analyze the stress characteristics around circular hole, characteristic distance was introduced. The concept was proposed by Whitney and Nuismer [9] from point-stress and average-stress failure criteria. In the point-stress

failure criteria, the characteristic distance was the length from the holes edge to the point where the stress equal to unnotched strength. In the average-stress failure criteria, characteristic distance was the length from edge to some point where the average stress was equal to unnotched strength. The point-stress failure criterion was easier to calculate and apply.

In order to improve the mechanical performance of specimens with open holes, different techniques were applied including flat braided composites method, moulding holes and needle punch process. To examine the property of flat braided composite with a circular hole, Asmi et al. [10] compared braided holes specimens and drilled holes specimens' properties. A Teflon pin was use during braiding process and molding process to make a circular hole. It can not only increase the fiber contents near a hole, but also keep the continuity of the fibers. It was found that the circular hole existed after final fracture compared with drilled holes specimens on which critical fracture was happened beside the hole. The maximum load of drilled specimens was 36% lower than unnotched specimens while only 17% for braided one. Zitoune et al. [11] compared different properties of carbon/epoxy composites between drilled and moulded holes. The molded hole was added via a pointed steel punch which was used to spread the fibers during the manufacture process of the composite plate and getting a circular space after polymerization. It was concluded that the fracture strength of molded hole specimens was 30% higher than drilled hole specimens. Also, the maximum deformation around drilled hole was twice higher compared to those of molded hole specimens according to the strain fields measurement obtained from three digital image correlation technique, which was considered that the fibers near the hole were higher compared to drilled specimens caused by molded process. Both these methods were realized to improve the properties through increase the fiber contents near the circular hole. However,

the methods complicated the molding process and increase the nonuniformity of the materials.

Needle punch process was widely used in textile area provided remark performance. The introduced thickness-direction fibers via needle punched process play an important role that provides excellent z-directional properties that minimizes delamination problem. Sung Ho Lee and Tae Jin Kang [12] studied the effect of changes in fiber structure on the mechanical properties of nonwoven composite with different punching densities. It was found after needle punch process the tensile strength and mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of nonwoven composite was increased with increasing punching density due to the increased fiber entanglement. The flexural impact, fatigue and wear properties were decreased with punching densities because of the damage to fiber during the punching process which resulted in the reduction of fiber length.

To monitor the damage process, acoustic emission (AE) is widely used in evaluating damage characteristics during mechanical properties tests. Xingmin Zhang and Xiong Yan [13] investigated different fracture behaviors bring about different AE signals responding on amplitude events. In the research, different events occurred inside the materials included fiber-matrix interfacial debonding, matrix plastic deformation and cracking, fiber pull-out, fiber breakage and interlaminar delamination was distinguished from acoustic emission events amplitude range 30-45 dB (low amplitude events), 30-60 dB (low amplitude events), 60-80 dB (middle amplitude events), 80-97 (high amplitude events) and 60-85 dB (middle amplitude events), respectively.

In this study, needle punch process was applied on chopped glass fiber mat in order to improve the properties of glass mat composite with circular holes. Normal glass mat (GM) and needle punched glass mat (NGM) were employed to fabricate composite with different volume fraction of glass fiber. Circular holes were drilled on the specimens. Decreasing of notched strength of drilled specimens from unnotched strength was compared between needle punched glass mat composite (NGMC) and glass mat composites (GMC). AE was also carried out to monitor the damage process during tensile test. The tensile results and fracture behavior were analyzed and discussed. Scan electron microscope (SEM) was used to analyze combination of z-directional fibers with matrix.

2 Materials and Experiment

2.1 Materials

Two kinds of composites made of GM and NGM were used as a comparison. The GM and NGM is shown in Fig. 1. Same E-CR glass fiber was used in both GM and NGM. For matrix, unsaturated polyester resin (Showa: RIGORAC 150HRBQNTNW) were employed as matrix. (Polymer was mixed with the hardener MEKPO (PERMEK N; NOF Corporation) in a ratio of 100:0.7).

Both of the two kinds of glass mat were used to fabricate composite plate by hand lay-up method. The thickness of the composites was controlled by spacers to get different volume fraction of glass fiber. After curing the resin in the room temperature for 24 hours, they were heated at 100 °C (for 2 hours) as post-cure.

After fabrication, the plate was cut into 20 mm-width and 30 mm-width specimens for unnotched and notched property test respectively. Each type was cut into 3 specimens according volume fraction of glass fiber contents. For notched one, 10 mm of drill was used to make a circular hole. Drilling speed was controlled at 2300 rad/min.

2.2 Tensile Test

Tensile test were performed by using an Instron universal testing machine under a speed of 1 mm/min. For the specimen with a hole, the notched strength was calculated by formula (1)

$$\sigma_N = \frac{F}{(W - D)T} \quad (1)$$

Where σ_N was notched strength which was a mean strength of notched specimen, F was maximum load, W was the width of specimen, D was the diameter of open hole, T was the thickness of specimen. A camera was employed to record whole process of tensile test. The dimension of unnotched and notched specimens is shown in Fig.2.

2.3 Acoustic Emission measurement

The AE testing equipment and test parameters were as follows: Physical Acoustic corporation Micro-30 sensors; 26dB preamplifiers having a bandwidth of 65 - 1100 KHz; system threshold of 25 dB; Peak definition time of 50 μ s ; hit definition time of 150 μ s ; hit lockout time of 300 μ s .After setting, the AE signals were captured during mechanical testing by the software named "AEwin for USB".

3 Results and conclusion

3.1 Damage process

The typical damage characteristic of GMC and NGMC were shown in Fig. 3. Both the materials experience similar process. During tensile test, due to stress concentration effect, the initial crack was happen at the edge of hole. Then the crack extended to outside in a relatively slow speed before some point after where the crack extended extremely fast. Finally, the specimens would be destroyed. Picture B and C are maximum load and just before failure state respectively. The damage specimens are shown in Fig. 4. In the figure, 4A and 4C are GMC specimens and 4B and 4D are NGMC specimens. For unnotched specimens, besides the major crack, many micro-cracks can be found on the specimens. The direction of most micro-cracks is distributed perpendicular to load direction. For NGMC materials, more micro-cracks can be found compared to GMC materials. For notched specimens, similar characteristics could be found. Most of the damage was concentrated near the hole in GMC materials. However, besides the major fracture, many micro-cracks can be found on the specimens in the case of NGMC materials.

3.2 Strength analysis of tensile test

The strength and notched strength of GMC and NGMC materials associated with volume fraction of glass fiber is shown in Fig.5. The trend line was drawn according to least square method. From the trend line, it was found that the strength of unnotched specimens of NGMC was lower compared to GMC at same volume fraction of glass fiber. But the notched strength of notched specimens held higher value compared to GMC. It was considered that z-directional fiber was introduced via needle punched process as well as the micro-fracture into NGMC. After hand layup fabrication, some small white points could be found near needle punched hole. These white points were caused from poor impregnation of z-directional fiber.

On the other hand, these z-directional fibers reinforced the materials in thickness direction which minimized the delamination during tensile test. Different fracture forms of notched specimens between GMC and NGMC was observed via optical microscope and illustrated in fig.6. The photo was taken from thickness direction. A line was marked to locate the circular hole position. It was found that the integrality was kept better in NGMC compared to GMC. The cracks which separated the materials

in thickness direction were found obviously in GMC. It was caused by delamination of notched GMC during tensile test which was proved that the z-direction was played an important role in resistance delamination in NGMC.

3.3 Acoustic Emission

During tensile test the AE measurement was applied to evaluate the damage process of GMC and NGMC. Counts events and amplitude from AE were used in here. The fracture in materials during tensile test is generated step by step. Energy release is different in different fracture forms which can be applied to distinguish different fracture occurred in materials via AE measurement. The main events occurred in composites that could be detected by AE include matrix cracks, fiber/matrix interface cracks, delamination, fiber pulled out and fiber breakage.

The tensile processes of unnotched specimens of GMC and NGMC together with AE measurement results are shown in Fig. 7. The volume fraction of GMC and NGMC specimens are 27.4% and 27.8% respectively. The strength of GMC was about 5% higher than NGMC. From AE measurement, the AE signal was little before 0.01 of strain in GMC. This is the typical elastic stage. But this stage for NGMC, the strain was around 0.005, half of the GMC. After that, the speed of AE counts accumulation was accelerated. When the process came into 0.01 to 0.02 of strain in GMC, the amplitude was mainly concentrated from 20dB to 60dB. It was considered that the damage was caused by matrix cracks and fiber/matrix interface damage. For NGMC, this stage was from 0.05 to 0.13 of stain. Then more damage occurred between 60 dB-100 dB which was considered as fracture from delamination, fiber pulled out and fiber breakage.

More counts event was occurred in NGMC materials compared to GMC. These counts events were mainly concentrated in 20 dB - 40 dB of whole tensile process and 60 dB – 80 dB at the end. That is the reason why many micro-cracks could be found on NGMC specimens after failure.

For notched specimens, the results are shown in Fig.8. It was found that the more damage happened at amplitude from 60 dB to 100dB in NGMC which was indicated that more stress was delivered to fibers and caused fibers breakage happened in NGMC. That is the reason why notched strength was higher in NGMC compared to GMC. Also the damage was more serious in NGMC which could found from failure specimens.

3.4 Scanning electron microscope observation of NGMC

The notched specimens of NGMC were chosen to be conducted SEM observation. The fiber breakage is shown in Fig. 9. Many fiber breakages could be found in NGMC specimens. However, many fibers in z-direction were pulled out after tensile test as shown in Fig. 10. This is mainly due to two reasons. First, the thickness was thin and the fibers in z-direction are relatively short. This situation could not provide enough interfacial force to break the fiber. Second, the impregnation between z-directional fiber and matrix were not so good compared to in-plan fibers.

4. Conclusion

In this study, in order to improve the resistance property of glass fiber reinforced composite on drilled hole, needle punching process was introduced. This process not only reduces length of fibers but also adds piercing fiber across different layers. 10mm of diameter drill was used to make a circular hole. Fracture behavior and tensile results were analyzed and compared with ordinary glass mat composite. The following conclusions were obtained in here.

1. From the results of tensile test, it was found that the strength of unnotched specimens of NGMC was decreased compared to GMC under the same volume fraction of glass fiber. But for notched specimens, the notched strength of NGMC was increased compared to GMC.
2. The optical observation showed that the delamination was decrease in NGMC compared to GMC due to the z-directional fibers introduced from needle punched process.
3. From the result of AE measurement, the matrix damage and fiber/matrix debonding was quite serious in NGMC which limited its property. It was considered that the poor interfacial property of z-directional fibers. On the other hand the fiber breakage was increased.
4. The fiber breakage and fiber pull out and was found in notched specimens of NGMC.

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Figure

Fig.2 Dimension of tensile specimens

Fig. 1 Glass mat and needle punched glass mat

A. Damage process of unnotched specimens of GMC

B. Damage process of unnotched specimens of NGMC
 Fig.3. Damage process of unnotched specimens

Fig.4. Failure specimen's comparison between GMC and NGMC

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Fig.5. Tensile test results of GMC and NGMC

A. Optical observation of notched specimen of GMC

B. Optical observation of notched specimen of NGMC

Fig.6 Optical observation of notched specimen

A. Stress-strain curve of unnotched specimens with AE counts accumulation

B. AE amplitude distribution of unnotched specimens of GMC

C. AE amplitude distribution of unnotched specimens of NGMC
Fig.7. Damage process measure by AE of unnotched specimens

A. Stress-strain curve of unnotched specimens with AE counts accumulation

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B. AE amplitude distribution of notched specimens of GMC

C. AE amplitude distribution of notched specimens of NGMC

Fig.8 Damage process measure by AE of notched specimens

Fig. 9 Fiber breakage of notched specimens in NGMC

Fig. 10 Fiber pulled out of notched specimens in NGMC